

Kinetics of Transformation of Outer Charge-Transfer Complexes to Inner Complexes

(Miss) BHARATI BHATTACHARJEE, (Mrs.) ANURADHA VARSHNEY and S. N. BHAT*

Department of Chemistry, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong-793 003

Manuscript received 12 May 1982, revised 1 March 1983, accepted 1 July 1983

Kinetics of transformation of outer charge-transfer complexes (methanol-iodine, ethanol-iodine, water-iodine and acetonitrile-iodine) to inner complexes are found to follow the first order rate law. The ease with which the transformation proceeds depends on the relative magnitudes of enthalpy of formation of the outer charge-transfer complexes.

MULLIKEN¹ pointed out that a donor-acceptor pair can form either an associative outer complex or a dissociative inner complex depending on the distance of approach between the donor and acceptor and the relative magnitude of the no-bond and dative wave functions. It was also suggested that the formation of the inner complex from the outer complex should be strongly dependent on environmental conditions. If the environmental influence is sufficiently great, the inner complex may become the stable form of the donor-acceptor pair, and with small or no environmental influence the outer complex may represent the stable form. One of the early evidences for the transformation of outer complex to the inner variety was the electrical conductance of iodine in pyridine which was explained² on the basis of the equilibrium.

Literature shows that in many donor-acceptor systems with halogen acceptors, the formation of trihalide ion is often noticed, which can result only through the formation of inner complexes from the initial outer complexes³. In view of the limited information available in the literature, we have investigated the transformation of a few outer complexes between n-donors with iodine, with particular reference to the factors affecting the formation of inner complexes.

Experimental

Ethanol, methanol, acetonitrile and iodine were purified by standard procedures⁴. Conductivity water was used as such. A known amount of iodine was dissolved in the required amount of solvent (alcohol, water or acetonitrile) which had already been kept in a thermostat jacketed bath (at the required temperature) and the electrical conductivity was noted at different temperatures. Concentrations of iodine in the solutions were also determined by titrating the iodine solutions with standard sodium

thiosulphate solution. The concentrations of iodine determined by both the procedures are the same and this indicates that iodine has not formed any new compound with the donor but is attached loosely (reversibly) to the donor.

As the above mentioned process (i.e., the transformation of outer complex into inner complex) occurs with a change in the number of ions present, the electrical conductivity changes and the measurement of the conductivity offers a convenient and accurate (assuming that conductivity and concentration have a simple relationship at high dielectric constant) means of following the course of the process. The time dependence of electrical conductance of the solutions at 25, 30 and 35° were measured by using Elico conductivity bridge (model CM-82) during the first half an hour. The temperature of the solution was maintained constant ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) using a thermostat. The velocity constant for the transformation of outer charge-transfer complex to inner complex was calculated using the first order rate constant. Since conductance is proportional to the concentration of ions, the velocity constant, k , is calculated from

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t_2 - t_1} \log \frac{\sigma_\infty - \sigma_{t_1}}{\sigma_\infty - \sigma_{t_2}}$$

where σ_∞ , σ_{t_1} and σ_{t_2} are the electrical conductances at infinite, t_1 and t_2 time, respectively. Each experiment was repeated at least twice and the results were reproducible within the error limit. The value of k was obtained from the least square treatment of the data. The energy of activation for the transformation was calculated from Arrhenius equation by plotting $\log k$ against $1/T$. The uncertainty in the value of E_a was generally ± 400 J/mole. Entropy of activation was found by using Eyring equation from absolute rate theory^{5,6}.

Results and Discussion

Ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol form 1:1 outer charge-transfer complexes with iodine with

λ_{CT} at ~ 225 and 220 nm, respectively. The equilibrium constants of formation in *n*-heptane were 0.95 and 0.65 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$, respectively at 25° while the enthalpy values were 13.388 and 12.552 kJ mole^{-1} , respectively⁷. Water-iodine on the other hand does not show any charge-transfer band above 220 nm. Bhowmik and Chattopadhyay⁸ reported that they could detect a band at 202.5 nm for water-iodine system*. These observations run parallel with ionization potentials of the donors. The equilibrium constant of formation of complex for iodine-water system at 25° is very low (0.0420^8 ; $1.4 \times 10^{-3} M^{-1}$)⁹. These results show that the stability of iodine-ROH systems vary in the order ethanol-iodine > methanol-iodine > water-iodine.

When iodine is directly dissolved in methanol, ethanol, water and acetonitrile (the dielectric constants are 32.5 , 24.3 , 78.5 and 36.7 , respectively) the initial electrical conductivities [1.32×10^{-6} , 3.1×10^{-6} , 1.3×10^{-6} (concn. = $0.00125 M$) and 5.8×10^{-6} mho M^{-1} at 25° for $0.05 M$ iodine in respective solvents] increase with time and reach maximum value in about 24 hr (Fig. 1). It is reported in the literature that the intensity of charge-transfer band decreases with time and accompanying the decrease in the

Fig. 1. Variation of electrical conductivity of iodine in ethanol at 25° .

intensity of the charge-transfer band, progressive intensification of the triiodide ion absorption (at 297 and 363 nm) is noticed. So it is felt that the time dependence of the electrical conductivity (i.e., increase in conductivity with time) is due to the

transformation of the initially formed 1:1 outer charge-transfer complex followed by the very fast reaction of the inner complex with iodine to form the triiodide ion.

The kinetics of transformation of the outer complexes of iodine namely $\text{CH}_3\text{OH.I}_2$, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH.I}_2$, etc. to the inner complexes were studied employing the time dependence of the electrical conductivities of the solutions. Since the formation of the triiodide ion from the inner complex is likely to be a fast step, the rate determining step will be the transformation of the outer complex to inner complex. The reactions are of pseudo first order and the rate constants are quite large. (It seems, in these cases the driving force is the solvation of ions formed). The rate data are summarised in Table 1 along with the values of energies and entropies of activation. The transformation of the outer complex of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH.I}_2$ to the inner complex is much slower and is associated with activation energy higher than that for the transformation of $\text{CH}_3\text{OH.I}_2$. It is interesting that the enthalpy value for the formation of the outer complex is also much lower in the latter case. In the case of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH.I}_2$ where the enthalpy ($-\Delta H^\circ$) value is large, the transformation would be expected to be much slower than $\text{CH}_3\text{OH.I}_2$. Water, on the other hand, seems to form a less stable outer complex with iodine which can be visualized due to high I.P. of water and very low $-\Delta H^\circ$ value for the outer complex⁸. The low $-\Delta H^\circ$ value facilitates the easier transformation of the outer complex to inner complex¹. The velocity constant for the transformation of outer complex of water-iodine to inner is $22 \times 10^{-6} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at 25° (concn. = $1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$) indicating that the transformation is quite fast. Similar case has been reported in the literature for triphenylphosphine-iodine in highly polar solvents¹⁰. On the basis of these findings, we feel that the value of the enthalpy for the transformation of outer complex ($-\Delta H^\circ$) determine the facility with which the transformation of outer to inner complex occurs. Acetonitrile forms an outer complex with iodine and the velocity constant and the activation energy for the transformation of the outer to the inner complexes are given in Table 1. Even though the interactions involved are $n-\sigma$ type it is not possible to compare the data with those of ROH.I_2 systems as ROH is intermolecularly hydrogen bonded system.

The entropy of activation is large and negative in all the systems studied. The negative ΔS^\ddagger values are indeed what one would expect in reactions involving ionization of neutral molecules. Since the transformation of the outer to the inner complex involves ionization, it is likely that the

*The authors are thankful to the referee for the literature reference.

TABLE 1—THE VELOCITY CONSTANT, ENTROPY OF ACTIVATION AND ACTIVATION ENERGY FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF OUTER CHARGE-TRANSFER COMPLEXES INTO INNER COMPLEXES
[IODINE]=0.05 M

System	Average K^\ddagger , $\text{sec}^{-1} \times 10^{+6}$			Average Entropy of Activation $-\Delta S^\ddagger$, $\text{JK}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}$	Activation Energy, E_a $\text{J/mole} \times 10^{-3}$	$-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ/mole
	25°	30°	35°			
Methanol-iodine	9.5	14	26	75.7	73.4	12.552
Ethanol-iodine	5.2	5.8	11	152.3	52.3	13.388
Water-iodine**	22.0	25	33	212.7	30.4	27.880#
Acetonitrile-iodine	7.0	9.0	13	162.2	48.5	7.949

**Concentration of iodine in water = 0.00125 M.

‡Error limit in the value of $K = \pm 0.002$.

#Calculated from E_a value.

activated complex is also similar to an ion pair, and will therefore be stabilized by solvation to a greater extent than the outer complex (initial state)⁶. The negative entropy indicates that the activated complex is less probable (and the reaction should be slower than normal) and the probability factor P is very low⁶. In the present case, methanol, ethanol and water already exist in a partially frozen state due to strong intermolecular forces—hydrogen bonding. We are not, therefore, in a position to comment on the reverse trend of activation energies when these solvents are used. The loss in entropy in an ionization includes the change in entropy of the complex (molecules) which ionizes and the change in entropy of the solvent molecules which surround the ions.

From the above study it appears that the rate determining step in the formation of triiodide ion is probably the transformation of the outer complex and it follows the first order rate law and the ease with which the transformation proceeds depends on the relative magnitudes of enthalpy of formation of the outer charge-transfer complexes. It is possible that in some cases the inner complex may be the more stable form, particularly in solvents favouring solvation of the inner complex or its ions.

Acknowledgement

The authors (A. V. and B. B.) are thankful to C. S. I. R., New Delhi for financial assistance, to

Prof. Junjappa and Prof. T. S. B. Narasaraju, Head, Chemistry Department, N.E.H.U., for facilities and encouragement.

References

- (a) R. S. MULLIKEN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 801.
(b) R. S. MULLIKEN and W. B. PERSON, "Molecular Complexes", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1969.
- R. S. MULLIKEN and C. REID, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 3869.
- S. N. BHAT and C. N. R. RAO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 3216.
- (a) S. M. BRANDON, M. TAMRES and S. SEARLES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 2129.
(b) A. I. VOGEL, "Practical Organic Chemistry", ELBS, London, 1973.
- (a) A. A. FROST and R. G. PEARSON, "Kinetics and Mechanism", 2nd Edn., Wiley International Edition, New York, 1961.
(b) S. GLASTONE, K. J. LAIDLER and EYRING, "Theory of Rate Process", Mc-Graw Hill Book Company, New York, 1941.
- S. W. BENSON, "The Foundation of Chemical Kinetics", Mc-Graw Hill Book Co., New York, 1960.
- C. N. R. RAO, S. N. BHAT and P. C. DWIVEDI, *Appl. Spectros. Revs.*, 1972, **5**, 1.
- B. B. BHOWMIK and S. P. CHATTOPADHYAY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **17A**, 85.
- J. D. BURGER and H. A. LIEBHAFSKY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1973, **45**, 600.
- K. R. BHASKAR, S. N. BHAT, SURJIT SINGH and C. N. R. RAO, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1915.